

Swelling of KEVLAR 49/Epoxy and S2-Glass/Epoxy Composites

S. Y. Lo¹, H. T. Hahn¹, T. T. Chiao²

- 1) Washington University, Campus Box 1087, St. Louis, MO 63130, U.S.A.
- 2) Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, L-338, Livermore, CA 94550, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

The moisture effect on S2-glass/epoxy and Kevlar 49/epoxy was investigated under the environments of 75°C/75% RH and 75°C/water.

S2-glass/epoxy was found to be unstable under these conditions; longitudinal cracking was observed and some material loss was found during the desorption process. The maximum moisture contents were ~0.31% at 75°C in 75% RH and ~0.412% at 75°C in water. The composite swelled transversely up to about 0.11% and 0.16% in the respective environments.

Kevlar 49/epoxy was more stable than S2-glass/epoxy; no material loss was found. However, the maximum moisture contents were ~2.47% at 75°C in 75% RH and ~5.5% at 75°C in water. The composite swelled transversely up to ~1.0% and ~2.23% in the respective environments. The results indicate that Kevlar 49 fibers swell substantially in the radial direction. Both composites exhibited a change in color after long-time exposure in the environments tested.

INTRODUCTION

The dimensional stability of structural materials is an important design consideration where environmental changes are encountered. The dimensional stability of composite laminates is directly related to the hygrothermomechanical properties of unidirectional composites.

The susceptibility of polymers to swelling due to moisture absorption also leads to the presence of residual stresses in the composite laminates. However, these stresses generally negate the curing stresses, hence combined effects may be beneficial. Thus it is important to know not only the moisture diffusion behavior but also the swelling behavior in order to properly characterize the material property changes, such as modulus or strength, resulting from moisture absorption.

In this paper, the swelling properties of S2-glass/epoxy and Kevlar 49/epoxy are studied. The diffusion behavior is described by using two models, i. e., one-phase (Fickian) and two-phase models. The swelling behavior of the composites is described by a model which is based on the assumption that the swelling

is negligible until the moisture concentration reaches a threshold value and then increases linearly thereafter.

The environments chosen are 75°C/75% RH and 75°C/water.

BACKGROUND

Two diffusion theories have been studied. The first is the classical single free phase model of absorption in which the water molecules are not bound to the material. The second, the Langmuir two-phase model, considers a free diffusion phase and a second bound phase which does not involve diffusion. Both these models employ the Fick's Law for the free-phase water so that the driving force of diffusion is the concentration gradient. In order to simplify the analysis of the diffusion equations, the following assumptions have been made:

(1) Lateral dimensions of specimens are much longer than thickness so that diffusion occurs only normal to the plane.

(2) The diffusivity, D , is constant inside the material.

The results of the one-phase (Fickian) model are found in (1). The moisture content, M , is related to diffusivity, D , by:

$$\frac{M-M_0}{M_\infty-M_0} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1}{(2j+1)^2} \exp \left[-\frac{\pi^2 D t}{h^2} (2j+1)^2 \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

where t and h are time and specimen thickness, respectively, and M_0 and M_∞ are the initial and final equilibrium moisture contents, respectively.

For short times, an approximation can be obtained as

$$\frac{M-M_0}{M_\infty-M_0} = 4 \left(\frac{D t}{h^2} \right)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) can be applied to determine the diffusivity of the material. Rearranging Eq. (2), we obtain the relationship between M and \sqrt{t} . The diffusivity is then given by

$$D = \frac{\pi}{16} \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{M_\infty - M_0} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

The two-phase diffusion model has been used in (2,3). With this model, besides the weight gain and diffusivity, two additional parameters are introduced, i. e.,

(1) the time rate of bound water being freed, denoted by b , and

(2) the time rate of free water being bound, denoted by a .

For $b, a \ll \frac{\pi^2 D}{h^2}$, the equation for moisture content is approximated by

$$\frac{M-M_0}{M_\infty-M_0} = 1 - \frac{a}{a+b} \exp[-bt] - \frac{b}{a+b} \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1}{(2j+1)^2} \exp \left[-\frac{\pi^2 D t}{h^2} (2j+1)^2 \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

Note that when $b \gg a$ the two-phase model approaches the one-phase model.

When the exposure time is small enough, Eq. (4) can be approximated by

$$\frac{M-M_0}{M_\infty-M_0} = \frac{b}{a+b} 4 \left(\frac{Dt}{\pi h^2} \right)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, for sufficiently large time, Eq. (4) can be approximated by

$$\frac{M-M_0}{M_\infty-M_0} = 1 - \frac{a}{a+b} e^{-bt} \quad (6)$$

Taking the natural logarithm of Eq. (6) and rearranging the terms, we have

$$\ln \left(1 - \frac{M-M_0}{M_\infty-M_0} \right) = \ln \frac{a}{a+b} - bt \quad (7)$$

By using Eq. (7), the parameters a and b can be determined. b is the slope in Eq. (7) and a can be found from the zero time intercept of the plot of

$$\ln \left(1 - \frac{M-M_0}{M_\infty-M_0} \right) \text{ versus time.}$$

The diffusivity can be calculated using Eq. (5). Equation (5) shows that the diffusivity, D_2 , for the two-phase model is related to the diffusivity, D_1 , for the one-phase model by

$$D_2 = D_1 \left(\frac{a+b}{b} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

In the experiments, $(M-M_0)$ is equal to the weight change from the start of each sorption test. However, in plotting the data we use the absolute value of $(M-M_0)$.

It has been suggested in (4) that the transverse swelling strain e_T^H could be described by

$$e_T^H = \begin{cases} \beta_T(c-c_v) & , \quad c > c_v \\ 0 & , \quad c < c_v \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Here c is the moisture concentration. Note that the moisture content M is equal to the average moisture concentration throughout volume. The threshold moisture concentration represents the amount of moisture that does not contribute to swelling.

The application of the laminated plate theory in conjunction with Eq. (9) shows that the linear portion of the e_T^H vs. M relation in an absorption test can be described by

$$e_T^H = \beta_T(M-c_v) \quad , \quad M > M_v \quad (10)$$

where M_v is related to c_v (4). Thus, the swelling coefficient can also be determined from an absorption test.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composites studied were S2-glass/epoxy and Kevlar 49/epoxy filament-wound at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory.

For S2-glass/epoxy, the epoxy was DER 332/Methane Diamine (100/24.5) cured for 2h at 150°C. The nominal fiber volume content was 65%.

For Kevlar 49/epoxy, the epoxy was DER 332/Kelpoxy-G 293/Hexlox 68/Tonox 60-40 (77/23/65/37.3), and the composite was cured at 60°C for 4-5h followed by a 3h postcure at 130°C. The nominal fiber volume content was 66%.

Square specimens 38 mm × 38 mm of $[0]_{2T}$ S2-glass/epoxy and $[0]_{4T}$ Kevlar 49/epoxy were cut from the large panels supplied. The square specimens were then preconditioned at 75°C in vacuum until no further weight loss was detected.

The environments used were 75°C/75% RH and 75°C/water. The 75% RH, which was created by using saturated sodium chloride solution [6], was placed at the bottom of a sealable desiccator and the specimens on the exposure rack at the top of the desiccator.

The swelling strains were measured using a micrometer with accuracy up to 0.0005", while the weights were measured on Mettler balance accurate up to 10⁻⁴ g. Both swelling and weight measurements were carried out at room temperature.

On the sorption curve, the initial linear portion of the curve was fitted by using the linear regression method while forcing the function to pass through the origin of the coordinates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

S2-Glass/Epoxy

Figure 1 shows the weight losses during preconditioning in vacuum. Some specimens were preconditioned first at 75°C and later at 100°C. For those specimens weight stabilized at 75°C but increased again when temperature was increased to 100°C. Also, the surface changed color from translucent white to brown with the period of preconditioning. The composite is not believed to be stable at 100°C.

The moisture diffusion behavior at 75°C/75% RH is shown in Fig. 2. The curves shown were calculated from the two diffusion models. The two-phase diffusion model seems to agree quite well with the data, better than the one-phase (Fickian) model. The second absorption data are quite close to the one-phase diffusion model while the first absorption and the desorption data deviate substantially from the one-phase model.

Table 1 shows the calculated diffusivities, one-phase and two-phase, with the appropriate moisture contents. Since the moisture content is based on one and the same initial dry weight, a negative moisture content in Table 1 indicates a loss of material which may be the result of leaching out of low molecular weight materials (5).

Suppose M_m and M_i are the contents of mobile and immobile moisture so that $M = M_m + M_i$. For absorption the ratio M_i/M_m approaches a/b as time increases, i. e., $M_i/M_m = a/b$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. From Table 1 we see that the immobile moisture content after the first absorption is ~44% of the mobile moisture content.

For desorption test a/b equals the initial, not the final, value of the ratio M_i/M_m . Since a/b for the first desorption is ~0.11, more moisture is believed to become mobile during desorption. The ratio further decreases to 0.08 for the second absorption. Thus, we can conclude that mobile fraction of absorbed moisture increases with moisture cycling. Consequently, the diffusion becomes closer to the Fickian type.

The equilibrium moisture content in the first absorption is seen to be ~0.31% at 75% RH. After saturation of moisture, desorption takes place at a

faster rate than the initial absorption with a slight permanent loss of material. Upon reabsorption, the weight change curve is somewhere between the initial absorption and the desorption curves. A similar phenomenon was observed in AS/3501 Gr/Ep laminate (4).

During the second absorption, the weight gain seems to reach an equilibrium momentarily and then starts to increase again. The delayed additional moisture absorption was also observed in other composites (6,7). However, the initial equilibrium weight gain in the second absorption is almost equal to the total weight loss in the desorption. Therefore, this value was used to calculate D.

As mentioned in the experimental procedure, the specimens were taken out of the environmental chamber into room environment to be weighed periodically and then returned to the 75°C environment. Thus, specimens have been subjected to a mild thermal cycling. However, the effect of the unintentional thermal cycling associated with the handling of the present specimens is not known.

Moisture absorption is known to lower the epoxy matrix glass transition temperature, T_g (5,8). When T_g is lowered below the maximum temperature of the thermal cycle, the resin will be highly viscoelastic. Therefore, internal stresses may result in permanent deformation and may accelerate the growth of small scale surface cracks and internal voids (5,6). Such cracking will increase moisture absorption in addition to the leaching out of low molecular weight materials.

Figure 3 shows the color difference between virgin, preconditioned and 75°C/75% RH specimens. There seems to be a permanent color change of the material from translucent white to brown with 75°C/75% RH specimen having the darkest color. This indicates that there is degradation of the epoxy matrix of the composite.

Figure 4 shows the comparison of the virgin, preconditioned, 75°C/75% RH, and 75°C/water specimens under transmitted light. The figure shows that there are cracks occurring along the fibers. These cracks are believed to occur in the fiber-matrix interfaces. Note that more cracks are found in the latter two specimens that were subjected to the moisture conditions.

Figure 5 shows a similar sorption behavior at 75°C/water. The curves shown were again calculated using the two diffusion models. Compared with 75% RH, the water immersion increased the equilibrium moisture contents as well as the permanent loss of material. The loss of material here was apparent by the sediments found in the water. However, the diffusivity is lower except for the second absorption where the diffusivity is higher.

The transverse swelling strains measured during the sorption tests are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. The longitudinal swelling strains were negligible, and hence not shown.

During the first absorption, the strain increases more slowly with the moisture content. When the moisture content exceeds about 0.1%, the strain increases fairly in proportion to the moisture content with a higher slope. The general trend of the three sorption curves is schematically shown in Fig. 8; the figure describes a hysteresis loop.

According to the theory (4), Eq. (10) is applicable to absorption while the same equation but with $M_v = c_v$ provides a good approximation for desorption.

Also, the theory cannot be used when there is a shrinkage upon complete desorption, as is observed of the present data. However, the overall trend of the data in Figs. 6 and 7 can be described by Eq. (10) with no restrictions on M. Therefore, the experimental data from the three sorption processes were fitted by the equation

$$e_T^H = \beta_T(M - M_V) \quad (11)$$

where M_V has no relation to c_V .

The transverse swelling coefficient does not change much from specimen to specimen although it depends on the type of environment. The average swelling coefficient at 75°C/water is higher than at 75°C/75% RH: 0.404 versus 0.334. On the other hand, the variation of M_V from specimen to specimen is substantial.

Several additional observations can be made about Figs. 6 and 7, namely that the composite is observed to shrink after the desorption. The amount of shrinkage depends on M_V such that a large M_V is associated with a large shrinkage, and vice versa. Also, the strain increase is very small when the moisture content reaches its equilibrium level as indicated by the almost flat portion of the curve at high moisture contents.

Kevlar 49/Epoxy

Figure 9 shows the weight losses during preconditioning for specimens with two different thicknesses. The specimens were preconditioned at 75°C in vacuum. The thick specimens (nominal thickness = 1 mm) show a weight loss of only 1.63% after 11 months, whereas the thin ones (nominal thickness = 0.5 mm) lose a maximum of 1.98%.

The moisture diffusion behavior at 75°C/75% RH is shown in Fig. 10: The curves shown were calculated using the two diffusion models. The second absorption is not complete yet. Since during the desorption no weight loss was observed, the maximum moisture content of the first absorption was used to calculate the diffusivity of the second absorption. Again, the model seems to work quite well. The absorption curves are close to the one-phase model, whereas the desorption curve deviates substantially from it. The specimens are believed to be more stable than S2-glass/epoxy at 75°C/75% RH.

Table 2 shows the calculated diffusivities for the one-phase and two-phase models with the appropriate moisture contents. The equilibrium moisture content in the first absorption is about ~2.47%. After saturation of moisture, the initial portion of desorption takes place at a faster rate than the initial absorption up to about 2% weight loss, then the rate decreases. However, no permanent loss of material is observed as happened with S2-glass/epoxy. Upon reabsorption, the weight change curve is somewhat between the initial absorption and desorption curves.

Figure 11 shows the color difference between virgin, preconditioned and 75°C/75% RH specimens. There seems to be a permanent color change of the material from yellow to brown with the 75°C/75% RH specimens having the darkest color. The same color change was also observed in the 75°C/water specimens. Bulk epoxy specimens were found to become darker when treated in the same environments (comparison not shown), whereas Kevlar 49 fiber did not change its color. Therefore, we can conclude that the color change in the composite is due to the degradation of epoxy matrix. However, no surface cracks were found under the microscope.

Figure 12 shows the sorption behavior at 75°C/water. The curves again represent the diffusion models. Since the specimens are not believed to be in equilibrium yet, the equilibrium moisture content was calculated to be ~5.5% by utilizing Eq. (7) and noting that, when time is large enough, the curve should be linear. The two-phase model deviates noticeably from the one-phase model. The two-phase model predicts that equilibrium moisture content would be attained after about one year of treatment, while the one-phase model predicts only about three months.

As observed, Kevlar 49/epoxy absorbs more moisture. Besides the epoxy

matrix, Kevlar 49 fiber is an organic fiber, and hence it has the ability to absorb moisture.

The transverse swelling strains measured during sorption tests are shown in Fig. 13. The longitudinal strains of the 75°C/water specimens are also shown in Fig. 14. The maximum transverse swelling strain in water is more than twice that at 75% RH. The swelling experiments in 75°C/water are not complete yet since the specimens have not reached equilibrium. The obtained data show the same trend as for S2-glass/epoxy in that the strain increases slowly with moisture content until it exceeds about 1%. Afterward, the strain increases fairly in proportion to the moisture content with a higher slope. Again, the three sorption curves in 75°C/75% RH all show a hysteresis loop.

There is a slight shrinkage in the material but no weight loss is observed. The average relationship is fairly linear, and can be described by Eq. (9) with $M_V = 0$ and $\beta_T = 0.41$.

Figure 14 shows that the strain in the longitudinal direction is negative with the up-to-date average strain of about $\sim -0.1\%$.

As indicated by Eq. (9), the transverse swelling coefficient should be determined by using moisture concentration, not moisture content. For a body of finite volume, equilibrium moisture content is equal to moisture concentration. Therefore, the equilibrium swelling data are replotted in Fig. 15 for both composites. The figure also includes the data for AS/3501 Gr/Ep from (4) for comparison purposes.

It is interesting that all the data regardless of the material system can be represented by a single straight line with a slope of ~ 0.43 . Also, the line passes very close to the origin. Thus, as a first-order approximation, the swelling behavior of the composites studied can be represented by $e_T^H = 0.43 c$. The reason for the applicability of such approximation, however, requires further investigation.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data obtained during the present investigation, the following conclusions can be made concerning the diffusion and swelling behavior of S2-glass/epoxy and Kevlar 49/epoxy composites:

- (1) The two-phase diffusion model is a better representation of the diffusion behavior of the two composite materials investigated.
- (2) Desorption process reveals a higher diffusion coefficient than absorption.
- (3) S2-glass/epoxy demonstrates its instability under the conditions applied. Some loss of material is accompanied by shrinkage during desorption process.
- (4) Kevlar 49/epoxy has been found to absorb moisture considerably more than S2-glass/epoxy. Also, it shows a considerable amount of swelling in the transverse direction. The swelling strain in the longitudinal direction is negative.
- (5) The relation between swelling strain and moisture content describes a hysteresis loop during moisture cycling. Higher strains are observed during desorption at the same moisture content.
- (6) The swelling behavior of both composites has been approximated by a linear equation.

(7) The relation between swelling strain and moisture concentration is fairly linear and only weakly depends on the material system. The reason for such behavior requires further study.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was performed under the auspices of the U. S. Department of Energy by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory under Contract W-7405-Eng-48.

REFERENCES

- (1) Springer, G. S., Ed., Environmental Effects on Composite Materials, Technomic Publishing Co., Inc., 1981.
- (2) Carter, H. G., and Kibler, K. G., "Langmuir-type Model for Anomalous Moisture Diffusion in Composite Resins," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 12, April 1978, 118-131.
- (3) Gurtin, M. E., and Yatomi, C., "On a Model for Two Phase Diffusion in Composite Materials," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 13, April 1979, 126-130.
- (4) Hahn, H. T., and Kim, R. Y., "Swelling of Composite Laminates," in Advanced Composite Materials--Environmental Effects, J. R. Vinson, Ed., ASTM STP 658, 1978, 98-120.
- (5) DeIasi, R., and Whiteside, J. B., "Effect of Moisture on Epoxy Resins and Composites," Advanced Composite Materials--Environmental Effects, J. R. Vinson, Ed., ASTM STP 658, 1978, 2-20.
- (6) Shirrell, C. D., "Diffusion of Water Vapor in Graphite/Epoxy Composites," Advanced Composite Materials--Environmental Effects, J. R. Vinson, Ed., ASTM STP 658, 1978, 21-42.
- (7) Whitney, J. M., and Browning, C. E., "Some Anomalies Associated with Moisture Diffusion in Epoxy Matrix Composite Materials," Advanced Composite Materials--Environmental Effects, J. R. Vinson, Ed., ASTM STP 658, 1978, 43-60.
- (8) McKague, L., "Environmental Synergism and Simulation in Resin Matrix Composites," Advanced Composite Materials--Environmental Effects, ASTM STP 658, J. R. Vinson, Ed., 1978, 193-204.

Fig. 1. Weight losses of S2-glass/epoxy during preconditioning

Fig. 2. Moisture sorption of S2-GI/Ep at 75°C/75% RH

Fig. 3. Color change in S2-glass/epoxy: (a) virgin specimen; (b) preconditioned at 75°C in vacuum for 6600 h; (c) second absorption at 75°C/75% RH for 3600 h; total preconditioning of 5880 h

Fig. 4. S2-glass/epoxy under transmitted light: (a) virgin specimen; (b) preconditioned at 75°C in vacuum for 6600 h; (c) second absorption at 75°C/75% RH for 3600 h; total preconditioning of 5880 h; (d) second absorption at 75°C/water for 2880 h; total preconditioning of 5880 h

Fig. 5. Moisture sorption of $[0]_{2T}$ S2-G1/Ep at 75°C/water

Fig. 6. Transverse swelling strain of $[0]_{2T}$ S2-G1/Ep at 75°C/75% RH

Fig. 7. Transverse swelling strain of $[0]_{2T}$ S2-G1/Ep at 75°C/water

Fig. 8. A schematic view of transverse strain vs. moisture content

Fig. 9. Weight loss of Kevlar 49/epoxy during preconditioning at 75°C/vacuum

Fig. 10. Moisture sorption of $[0]_{4T}$ Kevlar 49/epoxy at 75°C/75% RH

Fig. 11. Color change in Kevlar 49/epoxy: (a) virgin specimen; (b) preconditioned at 75°C in vacuum for 6600 h; (c) second absorption at 75°C/75% RH after 720 h; total preconditioning of 5160 h

Fig. 12. Moisture sorption of $[0]_{4T}$ Kevlar 49/epoxy at 75°C/water

Fig. 13. Transverse swelling strain of $[0]_{4T}$ Kevlar 49/epoxy at: (a) 75°C/75% RH; (b) 75°C/water.

Fig. 15. Transverse swelling strain vs. moisture concentration of S2-glass/epoxy, Kevlar 49/epoxy, and graphite/epoxy [4]

Fig. 14. Longitudinal swelling strain of $[0]_{4T}$ Kevlar 49/epoxy at 75°C/water

Table 1. Moisture diffusion parameters of S2-glass/epoxy at 75°C

	First absorption		First desorption		Second absorption	
	75% RH	Water	75% RH	Water	75% RH	Water
$M_0, \%$	0	0	0.310	0.412	-0.012	-0.076
$M_\infty, \%$	0.310	0.412	-0.012	-0.076	0.310	0.412
$b, 10^{-6}/s$	1.254	0.785	1.389	1.842	0.468	2.149
$a, 10^{-6}/s$	0.555	0.304	0.158	0.277	0.039	0.127
$D_1, 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^2/s$	18.35	9.26	91.44	69.25	28.62	35.17
$D_2, 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^2/s$	38.19	17.81	114.01	91.55	33.56	39.56

Table 2. Moisture diffusion parameters of Kevlar 49/epoxy at 75°C

	First absorption		First desorption		Second absorption	
	75% RH	Water	75% RH	Water	75% RH	Water
$M_0, \%$	0	0	2.470		0	
$M_\infty, \%$	2.470	5.50	0		2.470	
$b \times 10^{-6}$	1.039	0.133	0.696		0.545	
$a \times 10^{-6}$	0.404	0.084	0.246		0.046	
$D_1, 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^2/s$	19.99	5.86	38.88		26.87	
$D_2, 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^2/s$	35.58	15.61	71.26		31.60	